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Assessment of the awareness of patients with type 2 diabetes of their disease: A multi-center cross-sectional study in Lebanon

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Abstract

Background: This study aims to estimate the knowledge, attitude, and practices of patients with diabetes towards the disease and to assess the predictors of a higher awareness of diabetes. **Methods:** A multi-center cross-sectional study was performed targeting 384 patients from five endocrinology clinics in Lebanon. A self-reported survey was developed and validated and an awareness score was generated. **Results:** Around 18% of patients reported that they stopped taking diabetes medication when feeling good and 21.1% stopped them when in bad health status. In the case of hyperglycemia, 16.6% said that they doubled the dose of medication, and 14.6% stopped taking it when fasting. The mean awareness score of patients was 15.7 ± 3.9 over 25. After adjusting for covariates, The odds for higher awareness were 2.24 and 3.11 times higher among patients with higher education levels. These odds were 38% lower among patients with medical assistance at home. Physical activity significantly increased the odds of high awareness than those not practicing. **Conclusion:** Moderate awareness was noted among patients with lower knowledge of the symptoms of diabetes and good practices. **Practice implications:** Based on the findings of this study, healthcare stakeholders can explore the knowledge gaps and promote targeted interventions.

Keywords: Type 2 diabetes; Knowledge; Attitudes; Self-management; Patient education

Highlights

- Patients with type 2 diabetes in Lebanon had moderate awareness of diabetes.
- Poor self-management of medication was reported among patients with type 2 diabetes.
- Higher awareness of diabetes increased with higher levels of education, physical activity, and family history.
- Medical assistance at home and smoking significantly decreased the odds of higher awareness.
- The developed short 25-item tool can be applied in clinics to assess the awareness of patients with diabetes.

1. Introduction

The World Health Organization reported that type 2 diabetes (T2D) was the seventh cause of death worldwide, and its prevalence was estimated to increase substantially by 2030 [1, 2]. A recent report showed that diabetes contributed to around 11.2% of deaths globally, with the highest percentage in the Eastern Mediterranean region (16.2%) [3]. Higher mortality was found among patients with T2D in low- and middle-income countries, such as Lebanon [4]. This increased risk can be partially avoided through self-care and knowledge of the disease, namely its management, symptoms, complications, and recommendations [5, 6].

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Patients' awareness of T2D can help its early detection and prevention of severe adverse health outcomes that can adversely affect their quality of life [7]. Among others, early symptoms include thirst, frequent urination, fatigue, and blurred vision [8]. Patients should also be informed of the risk factors for developing the disease, such as positive family history, older age, obesity, sedentary lifestyle, and hypertension [9]. Accordingly, patients with T2D can optimize the management of diabetes by tackling the modifiable risk factors and increasing self-practices to control it [10]. Misinformation and misconceptions about diabetes can induce negative attitudes and behaviors, which calls for involving different healthcare providers (nurses, doctors, and pharmacists) to clarify these misconceptions [11]. Medication adherence can also impact diabetes management and can be promoted through optimal awareness of patients. Marital status (single or widowed) and abnormal hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) levels were found to be the main drivers of medication non-adherence [12].

Adequate communication that offers reassurance is crucial to the successful self-management of T2D [13]. A good understanding of patients and knowledge of the disease, its complications, and self-practices can help control the progress of T2D in addition to the clinical follow-up with healthcare professionals [14]. During the past two years, Coronavirus disease of 2019 (COVID-19) patients were prioritized [15], putting a high proportion of the population at risk of exacerbating their chronic conditions. Self-management of T2D derives from sufficient knowledge, attitude, and practices of patients that can be endorsed through support groups and continuing education to clarify misconceptions and encourage patients with T2D to share their experiences [16]. This study aims to estimate the knowledge, attitude, and practices of patients with T2D towards the disease and to assess the predictors of a higher awareness of diabetes. Based on the findings of this study, healthcare stakeholders can explore the knowledge gaps and promote targeted interventions.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Research design

A cross-sectional study was performed over six months (April-September 2021) targeting T2D patients from five endocrinology clinics in Lebanon.

2.2. Study sample and sample size

Adult T2DM patients were asked to participate in the study if they were diagnosed with diabetes for at least six months. No selection criteria were based on sex or ethnicity. Those with dementia or mental disorders making them unable to fill out the survey were excluded.

Epi-info was used to calculate the required sample size using the following equation:

$$N = \frac{(Z_{1-\alpha/2})^2 p(1-p)}{d^2}$$

Where Z is a standard normal variate ($Z_{1-\alpha/2} = 1.96$ at 95% confidence interval), d is the absolute accuracy or precision (5% margin of error), P is the expected proportion of the population with a specific outcome and was set at 0.5 (the advised value if the proportion in the population is not known). This yielded a required sample size of 384 patients.

2.3. Data collection

Two pharmacists approached the patients during the opening hours of the clinics. They described the study's aims orally and asked them to participate by completing a survey. The first page of the survey included the written objectives and consent form. The survey took around 12 minutes to be filled out.

2.4. Study tool

An existing questionnaire was used for data collection. This questionnaire was previously used for similar purposes on patients with T2D in Iran [17]. It was initially piloted on 30 patients, and questions that lacked clarity were either adjusted or deleted. The first part included questions about the general characteristics of the participants (sex, age, height, weight, area of residence (rural or urban area), level of education (illiterate, primary and high school or more), employment, and marital status, and the availability of house assistance and medical insurance). Age was classified into three categories: <50, 50-60, and >60). The Body Mass Index (BMI) of patients was calculated by dividing the weight (kilograms) by the square of height (meters) and then categorized as recommended [18]. The survey also collected the lifestyle habits of patients such as smoking, alcohol consumption, physical activity, and its frequency. Patients were

asked if the doctor recommended them a specific diet and if they followed his recommendations. Furthermore, they were asked if they usually add sugar to their drinks.

2.5. Medical history of the patients and clinical information

Patients were asked about the duration of diabetes diagnosis, family history, the latest laboratory results of HbA1c, and the frequency of testing it. They were also asked if they had a glucometer at home and whether they usually tested their serum glucose at fasting or two hours after meals. Participants reported other comorbidities such as hypertension, dyslipidemia, mental disorders, coronary artery disease, chronic kidney disease, thyroid dysfunction, and respiratory disease. They reported who diagnosed them with T2D (doctor or pharmacist) and their primary source of information regarding the disease. Patients were asked if they postponed their visits to the doctor, if the doctor explained the medication plan and whether they understood it, and if they knew or had any of the diabetes complications (retinopathy, neuropathy, cardiovascular, and nephropathy).

2.6. Self-management of medication of patients with type 2 diabetes

Patients were given different scenarios (See Table 3) to assess how they self-managed their medication (stopping, dose changing, no action). They were also asked about their behavior in case they missed a dose of their medication (taking it as soon as remembering, skipping the dose, contacting the doctor) and to suggest the best solution to avoid missing T2D medication (having it always, assistance from a close person, reminder or alarm and nothing can work).

2.7. Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of patients with type 2 diabetes

Patients were asked to answer a set of 36 questions, out of which those with poor inter-item correlation were deleted. Accordingly, a list of 13 knowledge, 6 attitudes, and 6 practice statements was generated (See Table 4). They had to answer each statement with “Agree”, “Disagree” or “I don’t know”.

2.8. Statistical analysis

Statistical analyses were computed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS Inc, Chicago, Illinois) Version 27. Based on the values of the skewness (0.052) and kurtosis (0.327), data are normally distributed and converge to their expected values [19]. Categorical variables are presented through frequencies and percentages. In contrast, the age, BMI, and the different scores are given through Means and Standard Deviations (SD). Negative questions were transformed into positive questions. Right answers for the knowledge, attitudes, and practices questions were given a score of 1, while they were given a score of zero if answers were incorrect or if patients answered with “I don’t know”. The maximum possible score for knowledge (13), attitude (6), and practice (6) was 25. The index had good reliability (Cronbach alpha 0.743) and positive inter-item correlations. After validating the scale (3 weeks), the survey was readministered to 30 patients to test its reliability. The percentage agreement between the two items for each question was acceptable. The mean value of the total score was taken as the cut-off point for the classification of the awareness (lower awareness if \leq Mean and higher awareness if $>$ Mean). Binary logistic regression was done to assess the predictors of a higher awareness producing Odd Ratios with a 95% Confidence Interval (CI). A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

2.9. Ethical considerations

This study used a survey for data collection without invasive procedures or interventions. The protocol, survey, and consent form were reviewed and approved by the institutional review board of the faculty of pharmacy of the Lebanese University. Legal approvals were obtained from the endocrinologists of the different clinics. Data were anonymous and non-identifiable, and data storage followed the university’s general data protection regulation guidelines. Written informed consent was obtained from each included participant.

3. Results

3.1. General characteristics of the patients

Overall, 431 patients were approached and 384 (89.1%) agreed to participate in the study. Table 1 presents the general characteristics of patients. Sex distribution was comparable between males (48.2%) and females (51.8%). The mean age of the sample was 58.3 (10.9) years distributed as follows: 19% were less than 50 years, 38% were between 50 and 60 years of age and the rest (43%) were older than 60. The mean BMI of the patients was 30.2 (5.4) with higher percentages of obese (48.3%) and overweight (37.2%) patients. Most patients were married (82.5%). Around 38% of patients were illiterate and 35.2% had a high school degree or more. As regards employment status, 48.3% did not

work, and the rest (51.7%) were either employed or benefited from retirement funds. Almost 40% of patients were current smokers and 10.2% were alcohol consumers. Doctors recommended special diets for most patients (96.9%) and only 22.4% followed the recommended diet.

Table 1 General characteristics and lifestyle habits of patients with Type 2 Diabetes

		Total (N=384)
General characteristics		Frequency (%)
Sex	Male	185 (48.2%)
	Female	199 (51.8%)
Age (years)	Mean (SD)	58.3 (10.9)
	<50	73 (19.0%)
	50-60	146 (38.0%)
	>60	165 (43.0%)
Body Mass Index (BMI) (kg/m ²)	Mean (SD)	30.2 (5.4)
	Underweight (<18.5)	2 (0.5%)
	Normal weight (18.5-24.9)	53 (13.8%)
	Overweight (25.0-30.0)	143 (37.2%)
	Obese (>30.0)	185 (48.3%)
Area of residence	Urban area	253 (65.9%)
	Rural area	131 (34.1%)
Marital status	Married	317 (82.5%)
	Single	28 (7.3%)
	Divorced/Widowed	39 (10.2%)
Level of education	Illiterate	144 (37.5%)
	Primary school	105 (27.3%)
	High school or more	135 (35.2%)
Employment	Do not work	183 (48.3%)
	Employed/retirement funds	196 (51.7%)
Medical assistance at home	Yes	167 (43.5%)
Medical insurance	Yes	276 (72.1%)
Lifestyle habits		Frequency (%)
Smoking status	Non-smoker/Former smoker	230 (59.9%)
	Smoker	154 (40.1%)
Alcohol consumption	Yes	39 (10.2%)
Physical activity	<150 min/week	81 (21.1%)
	≥150 min/week	64 (16.7%)
	Do not practice	239 (62.2%)
Recommended diet	Yes	372 (96.9%)
Are you following the recommended diet? (N=373)	Yes	86 (22.4%)
Do you add sugar to your drinks?	Yes	83 (21.6%)

Results are given in frequency (percentage) or Mean (SD); SD: Standard deviation, BMI: Body Mass Index

Table 2 Medical history of the patients and clinical information

		Total (N=384)
Medical history and clinical information		Frequency (%)
Duration of diabetes (years)	Mean (SD)	8.2 (7.5)
Family history	Yes	266 (69.3%)
HbA1c value (%) (N=373)	<7%	131 (35.1%)
	≥7%	242 (64.9%)
Frequency of HbA1c testing (months)	3-6 months	231 (60.2%)
	12 months	122 (31.8%)
	>12 months	31 (8.0%)
Glucometer at home	Yes	281 (73.2%)
Fasting blood glucose measurement (N=376)	Yes	224 (59.6%)
Blood glucose measurement 2h after meals (N=376)	Yes	110 (29.3%)
Comorbidities (N=378)	Hypertension	226 (59.8%)
	Dyslipidemia	221 (58.5%)
	Mental disorders	50 (13.2%)
	Coronary artery disease	39 (10.3%)
	Thyroid dysfunction	39 (10.3%)
	Chronic kidney disease	29 (7.7%)
	Respiratory disease	17 (4.4%)
Who diagnosed you with T2D?	Doctor	355 (92.4%)
	Pharmacist	29 (7.6%)
Main source of information regarding T2D (N=329)	Doctor	270 (82.1%)
	Pharmacist	59 (17.9%)
Frequency of follow-up with your doctor (N=356)	1-6 months	211 (59.3%)
	6-12 months	104 (29.2%)
	>12 months	41 (11.5%)
Do you usually postpone your visit to the doctor? (N=356)	Yes	161 (45.2%)
Did the doctor explain to you the medication plan? (N=356)	Yes	334 (93.8%)
Did you understand the doctor's explanation? (N=356)	Yes	248 (69.7%)
Did the doctor explain to you the causes and complications? (N=378)	Yes	236 (62.4%)
Have you ever had any diabetes-related complications? (N=378)	Yes	177 (46.8%)
Complications (N=177)	Retinopathy	83 (46.9%)
	Neuropathy	78 (44.1%)
	Cardiovascular	61 (34.4%)
	Nephropathy	28 (15.8%)

Results are given in frequency (percentage) or Mean (SD); SD: Standard deviation, HbA1c: Hemoglobin A1c

The mean duration of diabetes among the sample was 8.2 (7.5) years. Around 70% of patients had a family history of T2D and 64.9% had an HbA1b value of 7% or more. Most patients (73.2%) had a glucometer at home. As regards blood glucose measurement, 59.6% said that they measured it at fasting time and only 29.3% measured it two hours after meals. The most common comorbidities among patients were hypertension (59.8%) and dyslipidemia (58.5%). Most patients reported that a doctor diagnosed them with T2D (92.4%) and was their main source of information (82.1%) and almost 45% declared that they usually postponed their appointments. Doctors explained the medication plan for most patients (93.8%) and 69.7% reported that they understood the explanation. Around 47% of patients had T2D complications, out of which retinopathy (46.9%) and neuropathy (44.1%) were the most common (Table 2).

Table 3 presents the medication self-management of patients with T2D. Around 18% of patients reported that they stopped taking diabetes medication when feeling good and 21.1% stopped them when in bad health status. In the case of hyperglycemia, 16.6% reported that they doubled the dose of medication and 14.6% stopped taking the medication when fasting. Most patients (91.9%) agreed that treatment improved their health. Nevertheless, 26.3% reported that they could not always afford to buy it. A higher proportion of patients (44.1%) declared that they skipped the dose if they forgot to take it and 29.5% said they took it as soon as they remembered. Around half of the patients (51.4%) reported that nothing worked to avoid missing doses of diabetes medication and 31.7% reported that carrying the drugs was the best solution.

Table 3 Self-management of medication among patients with type 2 diabetes

Do you agree with the following statements?		
I stop taking my medication when I am in good health status (N=356)	Yes	63 (17.7%)
I stop taking my medication when I am in bad health status (N=356)	Yes	75 (21.1%)
I double the dose of medication in case of hyperglycemia (N=356)	Yes	59 (16.6%)
I stop taking the medication when fasting (N=356)	Yes	52 (14.6%)
I usually forget to take my medication during trips (N=356)	Yes	61 (17.1%)
I cannot always buy the medication because it is expensive (N=369)	Yes	97 (26.3%)
I never stop taking my medication (N=369)	Yes	149 (40.4%)
Treatment improves T2D patients' health (N=369)	Yes	339 (91.9%)
Self-management of drug-related issues		
What do you do if you missed a dose of your medication? (N=356)		
I have never missed a dose		88 (24.7%)
I take it as soon as I remember.		105 (29.5%)
I skip the dose		157 (44.1%)
I contact my doctor		6 (1.7%)
Best solution to avoid missing a dose of your medication? (N=356)		
To always carry the drug		113 (31.7%)
To ask a family member/friend for a reminder.		57 (16.0%)
Putting an alarm on the phone		3 (0.8%)
Nothing works		183 (51.4%)

Results are given in frequency (percentage); T2D: Type 2 diabetes.

Table 4 presents each statement's means of individual patients' knowledge, attitudes, and practice scores. Overall, patients had a total score of 15.7 (3.9) over 25. Of knowledge statements, higher scores were noted for those related to the fact that T2D is a lifelong disease (0.84), can be treated by oral drugs or insulin (0.89), and cannot be transmitted by contacting another patient (0.81). Most patients agreed that regular exercise (0.82), weight control (0.90), dietary modifications (0.89) and self-monitoring of blood glucose (0.89) can help manage diabetes. As regards practices, fewer patients have undergone eye (0.47) and foot examination (0.36) and were able to maintain a normal weight (0.53). A

high proportion of patients answered many questions with “Do not know”, namely those related to the fact that both sexes can have T2D with a higher risk for women and that it requires regular follow-up.

Table 4 Knowledge, attitudes, and practices of patients with T2D

	Agree	Disagree	Do not know	Score/1
Knowledge of T2D (N=384)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Mean
T2D is a lifelong disease	322 (83.9%)	25 (6.5%)	37 (9.6%)	0.84
T2D can be transmitted by contacting other patients	3 (0.8%)	312 (81.3%)	69 (18.0%)	0.81
T2D can be genetic	265 (69.0%)	112 (28.9%)	7 (2.1%)	0.69
T2D mostly affects adults and elderly	189 (49.2%)	62 (16.1%)	133 (34.6%)	0.49
Both sexes can have T2D	196 (51.0%)	83 (21.6%)	105 (27.3%)	0.51
Women have a higher risk of T2D	237 (61.7%)	42 (10.9%)	105 (27.3%)	0.62
T2D is characterized by high blood glucose levels	287 (74.7%)	10 (2.6%)	87 (22.7%)	0.75
Patients with T2D loose or gain weight	29 (7.6%)	305 (79.4%)	50 (13.0%)	0.08
Patients with T2D have frequent urination	124 (32.3%)	210 (54.7%)	50 (13.0%)	0.32
Patients with T2D have a frequent thirst	47 (12.2%)	285 (74.2%)	52 (13.5%)	0.12
T2D can be prevented	209 (54.4%)	124 (32.3%)	51 (13.3%)	0.54
T2D can be treated by oral drugs or insulin	342 (89.1%)	25 (6.5%)	17 (4.4%)	0.89
T2D requires regular follow-up	267 (69.5%)	4 (1.0%)	113 (29.4%)	0.70
Attitudes about T2D (N=384)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Mean
Regular exercise can help self-managing diabetes	315 (82.0%)	25 (6.5%)	44 (11.5%)	0.82
Weight control can help self-managing diabetes	347 (90.4%)	18 (4.2%)	21 (5.5%)	0.90
Dietary modification can help self-managing diabetes	343 (89.3%)	22 (5.7%)	19 (4.9%)	0.89
Patients should monitor their own blood glucose at home	344 (89.6%)	26 (6.8%)	14 (3.6%)	0.89
Patients with controlled T2D can have a normal life	279 (72.7%)	62 (16.1%)	43 (11.2%)	0.73
Patients with controlled T2D can have eating restrictions	153 (39.8%)	158 (41.1%)	73 (19.0%)	0.40
Practices (N=384)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)	Mean
I test the HbA1c levels at least once a year	354 (92.2%)	30 (7.8%)	--	0.92
I follow a low-sugar diet	266 (69.3%)	53 (13.8%)	65 (16.9%)	0.69
I try to have or maintain a normal weight	204 (53.1%)	156 (40.6%)	24 (6.3%)	0.53
I take the medication prescribed by my doctor	259 (67.4%)	125 (32.6%)	--	0.67
I undergo eye examinations at least once a year	182 (47.4%)	202 (52.6%)	--	0.47
I undergo foot examination at least once a year	138 (35.9%)	246 (64.1%)	--	0.36
		Total score/25	Mean (SD)	15.7 (3.9)

Results are given in frequency (percentage), and the total score is given in Mean (SD); SD: Standard deviation, T2D: Type 2 diabetes; HbA1c: emoglobin A1c

After categorizing patients according to their awareness scores, 162 patients (42.2%) had lower awareness, and 222 (57.8%) had higher awareness. Table 5 shows the predictors of higher awareness scores among patients with T2D. After adjusting for covariates, the odds for higher awareness were 2.24 (OR 2.24, 95% CI 1.30-3.89; p=0.004) and 3.11 (OR

3.11, 95% CI 1.83-5.27; $p < 0.001$) times higher among patients with primary school and high school or more respectively compared to illiterate patients. These odds were 38% lower among patients with medical assistance at home (OR 0.62, 95% CI 0.38-0.99; $p = 0.049$) than those without it. Furthermore, smokers had 38% lower odds of higher awareness than non-smokers (OR 0.62, 95% CI 0.39-0.97; $p = 0.042$). Patients with a physical activity < 150 minutes per week had significantly greater odds of high awareness than those not practicing (OR 2.46, 95% CI 1.48-3.94; $p = 0.005$). The odds of a higher awareness were 2.42 times higher among patients with a family history of diabetes than others (OR 2.42, 95% CI 1.48-3.94; $p < 0.001$).

Table 5 Predictors of a higher awareness score among patients with type 2 diabetes

Variables	Unadjusted model		Adjusted model	
	OR [95% CI]	p-value	OR [95% CI]	p-value
Female sex (male as reference)	0.66 [0.41-1.05]	0.080	0.68 [0.42-1.09]	0.109
Age (<50 as reference)				
50-60 years	0.91 [0.51-1.65]	0.765		
>60 years	0.50 [0.28-0.89]	0.018		
Rural residence area (urban as reference)	0.76 [0.50-1.17]	0.212		
Marital status (Single as reference)				
Married	0.97 [0.44-2.14]	0.936		
Divorced/Widowed	0.41 [0.15-1.10]	0.075		
Level of education (Illiterate as reference)				
Primary school	1.96 [1.18-3.27]	0.010	2.24 [1.30-3.89]	0.004
High school or more	3.74 [2.26-6.20]	<0.001	3.11 [1.83-5.27]	<0.001
Employment (Do not work as reference)				
Employed/retirement funds	1.01 [0.67-1.52]	0.962		
Medical assistance at home (No as reference)	0.63 [0.42-0.95]	0.028	0.62 [0.38-0.99]	0.049
Medical insurance (No as reference)	0.72 [0.46-1.15]	0.169		
Smoker (Non-smoker as reference)	0.59 [0.39-0.89]	0.011	0.62 [0.39-0.97]	0.042
Alcohol drinker (No as reference)	0.75 [0.38-1.45]	0.385		
Physical activity (No as reference)				
<150 min/week	3.17 [1.76-5.69]	<0.001	2.46 [1.32-4.58]	0.005
≥ 150 min/week	1.69 [0.97-2.94]	0.063	1.56 [0.84-2.88]	0.155
Family history (No as reference)	2.37 [1.52-3.68]	<0.001	2.42 [1.48-3.94]	<0.001
HbA1c $\geq 7\%$ (<7% as reference)	0.74 [0.48-1.15]	0.178		

* Higher awareness score with baseline answer "lower awareness" **OR: Odds Ratio; CI: Confidence interval; ***omnibus test ($p < 0.001$), Nagelkerke r square (0.202), Hosmer & Lemeshow ($p = 0.017$)

4. Discussion

This study explored the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of 384 patients with T2D regarding the disease and assessed the predictors of higher self-awareness. Overall, moderate awareness was noted among patients with lower knowledge of the symptoms of diabetes and good practices. A high proportion of patients answered with "I don't Know" many questions reflecting the need for interventions for patient education. The odds of a higher awareness were increased with higher levels of education compared to illiterate patients, among those practicing sports, and those with a family history of diabetes compared to others. Nevertheless, medical assistance at home and smoking significantly decreased these odds.

Around 65% of patients had an HbA1c value of 7% or more, which emphasizes the poor control of diabetes and could probably be associated with lifestyle habits or non-adherence to medication. Doctors were the main source of information regarding T2D. Most patients reported that doctors explained their medication plan, but not all understood it. This can partially explain the moderate awareness of patients about T2D and call for the need to provide workshops tailored for patient education [20], and include it in the continuing education program of healthcare providers [21, 22]. Almost 45% of patients postponed their medical appointments, which can exacerbate diabetes complications and highlight the need for strict lifestyle and behavioral interventions [23]. It could be also related to the concurrence of the pandemic with the data collection period and the fear of this highly susceptible group of adverse health outcomes [24, 25]. Most patients had a glucometer at home and measured their fasting blood glucose levels. A recent meta-analysis showed an association between the presence of a glucometer at home and good medication adherence [26], in contrast with the findings of this study. Several barriers such as the cost of the strips, fear of needles, pain, and lack of knowledge could have influenced the limited use of the glucometer after meals [27].

Many malpractices were noted in terms of medication self-management among patients with T2D. Among others, discontinuing the medication when feeling good, doubling the dose in case of hyperglycemia, and forgetting to take medication during trips were frequently observed. Non-adherence to diabetes medication was also reported in the literature and was primarily related to side effects, self-perceived drug efficacy, and weight gain [28]. Although the reasons for these practices were not assessed in this study, patient counseling and awareness programs can improve adherence and as a result, the management of diabetes. Around 26% of patients reported that they could not afford diabetes drugs. Previous research also reported cost-related medication challenges [29]. These challenges can be managed by promoting low-cost generic drug prescription [30], and clarifying misconceptions to increase their acceptance and use [31]. Around half of the sample said that nothing improved their medication adherence. Despite the evidence-based effectiveness of interventions such as reminders, electronic drug monitoring, and providing incentives [32], the negative attitudes of patients in this study could be related to their lower education level and other comorbidities, which increased the odds of polypharmacy.

Low awareness scores were found for statements related to the symptoms of diabetes, such as weight changes, frequent urination, and thirst. These findings were also reported in a similar study published in 2018 in Bangladesh [33], which could reflect low levels of health literacy among patients with T2D in Lebanon. A high proportion of patients answered with “I don’t Know” many questions, particularly those targeting the risk factors of diabetes. Although some of these factors were non-modifiable risks, adequate knowledge can help prone patients to focus on practices and lifestyle changes to prevent and control their conditions. Patients with higher levels of education had significantly increased odds of higher awareness than illiterate patients. Research showed similar results [34], where the language barrier and the fear of being singled out were the main barriers [35]. Those with medical assistance at home had lower awareness of T2D, possibly due to their reliance on another person for the management of their cases. Physical activity significantly increased the odds of higher awareness. A healthier lifestyle could explain this finding given that good practices are mostly associated with higher awareness. More than two-thirds of patients in this study had a family history of diabetes and had higher awareness scores than other patients. In contrast with the findings of another study [36], having another member of the family with diabetes could have promoted support between them and information sharing.

This study had limitations. Recall bias may have been induced since a self-reported survey was used for data collection. Interviewer bias was reduced since the data collectors were uniformly trained and did not interfere with the patient’s answers. Moreover, data coding and analysis were performed by a different researcher, which minimized the subjectivity of data collectors. Although the sample size was enough, patients were recruited from only five clinics which may affect the extrapolation of the results to other patients. A nationwide longitudinal study is recommended to allow better external validity and representativeness of Lebanon.

5. Conclusion

Patients with T2D in Lebanon had moderate awareness of diabetes. A lack of knowledge was found for some risk factors and was translated into bad practices regarding the follow-up of complications. Predictors of higher awareness can help target patients with certain characteristics to improve their knowledge, attitudes, and practices. The short 25-item tool used in this study can be applied in clinics to assess the awareness of patients with T2D. Accordingly, informed interventions and awareness campaigns can be developed.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Statement of ethical approval

The study protocol, questionnaire was reviewed and approved by the institutional review board of the faculty of pharmacy of the Lebanese University.

Statement of informed consent

Informed Consent form were reviewed and approved by the institutional review board of the faculty of pharmacy of the Lebanese University.

Authors' contributions

- GH: Conceptualization, formal analysis, Validation, and Writing-original draft;
- ZS and DM: Data curation, methodology, and writing-original draft;
- AAH: Methodology, project administration, writing-original draft;
- SR: Conceptualization, Methodology, and Writing-original draft;
- DK and SZ: Conceptualization, data curation, methodology, Writing-review, and editing
- All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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